

When Worlds Collide: Creating a Design Framework for Learning Mechanics in Archaeological XR Applications

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While numerous evaluation studies have been performed on the effectiveness of VR applications for education in the field of engineering and science (see e.g. Luo et al., 2021), the number of empirically-based studies within education in humanities disciplines is still very limited (Waagen et al, 2024). Even though literature on the affordances of 3D environments exists, this research has been criticized as being "derived essentially from thought experiments" within small team of researchers (Bower & Sturman, 2015). In addition, in their systematic review on design elements of XR applications, Radianti et al. (2020) argue that it is not even possible to formulate best practices, e.g. due to a lack of integration of learning theory and evaluation of learning outcomes. Therefore, actual knowledge on how to design effective XR applications in general, let alone in humanities education, is few and far between.

To help bridging this research gap, we present a starting framework for the analysis and creation of VR applications for education. We take inspiration from two main sources. First, we base ourselves on a large-scale systematic review of empirically-based VR articles in Humanities education (Huurdeman & Waagen, forthcoming). Second, we gain inspiration for the creation of the framework from the research area of serious game design. In this domain, Arnab et al. (2015) devised the *Learning Mechanics – Game Mechanics* model, which directly connects learning mechanics with concrete game mechanics. The model's learning mechanics include for instance tasks, activities and goals derived from existing pedagogical approaches.

Our framework, *Learning Mechanics in XR (LearnMiXR)*, connects learning mechanics and design elements for educational VR applications. We contextualize our framework using six archaeology-specific case studies from our prior literature review, demonstrating how the framework can be used to analyze existing learning-focused XR applications. Archaeology is chosen as an initial focal point due to the intrinsically spatial nature of this field. Furthermore, we tentatively highlight how our framework facilitates the design of new XR applications in archaeology, and potentially in a broader humanities setting. Via our paper and presentation, we intend to open up a discussion at the intersection of archaeology, educational sciences and human-computer interaction.

References

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